

CASE REPORT

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FREQUENCY OF TYPES OF GLAUCOMA PRESENTING TO TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL

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Background: “Glaucoma” is one of the primary causes of permanent blindness amongst the age-related ocular disorders, and its classification remains obscure. **Objectives:** To find out the frequency of types of “glaucoma” in patients presenting at the outdoor department. **Methods:** A “cross sectional study” was conducted in the Department of Ophthalmology, Hayatabad Medical Complex, Peshawar. The study duration was six months. The study was conducted on 117 patients of both genders having glaucoma in any one or both eyes for more than six months. The age group ranged from 30 to 70 years, with mean age of 53.068 ± 7.62 years and mean weight was 82.444 ± 5.59 Kg. All patients underwent eye examinations twice, which were conducted by the consultant “ophthalmologist”. Humphrey FDT visual field analyzer was used for visual field testing. Supra threshold (C20-5 or C20-1) screening mode” was used to screen all the participants involved, after the procedure was explained and demonstrated to them. Both eyes underwent individual testing with no correction. Types of “glaucoma” were noted. **Results:** Most of patients had primary open angle glaucoma (POAG) accounting for 34.2% of cases followed by primary angle closure glaucoma (PACG) being 6% whereas 7.7% of patients had secondary glaucoma. **Conclusions:** Our study demonstrated that majority of patients presented with POAG. Also, we found that secondary glaucoma and primary angle closure glaucoma mostly resulted from operational cataract procedures.

Keywords: Glaucoma; Primary Angle Closure Glaucoma; Secondary Glaucoma; Primary Open Angle Glaucoma

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INTRODUCTION

Most ocular diseases are common amongst specified age groups. Diseases such as diabetes related retinopathy, macular degeneration, glaucoma and cataracts are more common in older patients (1). Different ethnic backgrounds and socioeconomic statuses are one of the reasons why such diseases have variable prevalence (2–4). “Glaucoma” is the driving cause of permanent blindness globally, amongst age related ocular diseases (5) and its classification is riddled with disparities. A definitive definition for “glaucoma” has been put forward by the “International Society for Geographical and Epidemiological Ophthalmology” for epidemiological purposes by including several empirical factors, such as visual field losses and optic nerve head findings. Hence, “glaucoma” is a broad term that's utilized to portray a complex set of visual diseases with multi-factor etiology. Continued loss of “ganglion cells” in the retina linked with specific morphological changes to the optic nerve and changes in the visual acuity can be used to define “glaucoma” (6). Most patients have late diagnosis or are only examined after significant area of “visual field” is lost; this is because “glaucoma” is asymptomatic until it's in its late stages. Glaucoma can be categorized into primary and secondary types. Although the bimolecular mechanisms are poorly understood; family history, intraocular pressure and age constitute the major risk factors for primary glaucoma (7–9). “Secondary glaucoma” is thought to be a diverse group of diseases due to other eye pathologies, mechanical trauma, steroid use or other conditions including ‘pigment dispersion or pseudo exfoliation’ (10).

According to universal classification, primary glaucoma can be classified as Primary Open Angle Glaucoma (POAG) and Primary Angle Closure Glaucoma (PACG). Among these, POAG is more common while PACG is more prevalent in certain racial groups such as in Africa and South East Asia. (5, 9). In 2014, a meta-analysis found that in people between age of 40 and 80 years, prevalence of both PACG and POAG was about 4% (5). Another systematic review stated that the prevalence of “POAG” is comparatively greater in African ethnicities aged greater or equal to 40 years, with an approximated prevalence of 2%–4% (5,11). Furthermore, compared to other ethnic groups, adult Asian populations had a greater prevalence of “PACG”, approximately 1% (5, 9). Similarly, a study conducted has reported that the frequency of

POAG was 30.5%, while that of “Secondary glaucoma” was 7.8% and PACG stood at 5.1% in Nigeria (12). Another research shows that the frequency of POAG, PACG, and “Secondary glaucoma” were 1.7%, 1.5% and 0.8% respectively(13).

There is lack of local research data in this particular subject when considering our population. Only one research article has been found regarding this topic, which was conducted in Karachi (14),it only deals with prevalence of POAG. Furthermore, results of international researches cannot be portrayed over our local population, as the results are variable and contradictory (12, 13). Thus, this research was aimed at determining the frequency of types of “glaucoma” in patients presenting to outdoor department. Result of this study will not only generate local evidence on the topic, but also pave the way for further research in this subject.

METHODS

Our particular study was cross sectional study. A sample consisting of 117 participants was collected in the Department of Ophthalmology, Hayatabad Medical Complex, Peshawar. This study was conducted from 10th August 2019 to 10th January 2020. After taking permission from the ethical review committee and research department, patients between the ages 30-70 years of both genders with “Glaucoma” as per operational definition in any one or both eyes for more than 6 months were included in the research. “Non-probability consecutive sampling” was used as the sampling technique.

Patients with history of hypertension, macular degeneration, cataracts, significant corneal surface pathology, phthisis (by ocular examination), and participants unable to fixate by ocular examination and patients who refused informed consent were not included the study.

Base line demographic information of patients (age, gender, affected eye side (right/left), weight on weighing machine) was taken. All patients underwent eye examinations twice, which were conducted by the consultant “ophthalmologist”. To test visual fields of participants, we used a ‘Humphrey FDT visual field analyzer’ (15). To screen participants, supra-threshold mode of screening was used after the procedure was explained and demonstrated to them. Both eyes underwent individual testing with no correction. Types

of “glaucoma” were noted. Data collected was analyzed by SPSS version 22. Participation was entirely voluntary. Patient confidentiality and safety was ensured.

RESULTS

	Frequency	Percentage
POAG	40	34.2%
PACG	7	6%
Secondary Glaucoma	9	7.7%
Total	56	47.9%

Table 1. Frequency and percentage of patients according to type of glaucoma (n=117)

Stratification of “POAG”, “PACG” and “Secondary Glaucoma” with regards to “age” and “gender” are shown in Table 2, 3,4,5,6 and 7 respectively.

Age (Years)	POAG		P value
	Yes	No	
30-50	20(40.8%)	29(59.2%)	0.199
51-70	20(29.4%)	48(70.6%)	
Total	40(34.2%)	77(65.8%)	

Table 2. Stratification of “POAG” with respect to age

Gender	POAG		P value
	Yes	No	
Male	32(34.4%)	61(65.6%)	0.921
Female	8(33.3%)	16(66.7%)	
Total	40(34.2%)	77(65.8%)	

Table 3. Stratification of “POAG” with respect to gender

Age (Years)	PACG		P value
	Yes	No	
30-50	2(4.1%)	47(95.9%)	0.462
51-70	5(7.4%)	63(92.6%)	
Total	7(6%)	110(94%)	

Table 4. Stratification of “PACG” with respect to age

Gender	PACG		P value
	Yes	No	
Male	6(6.5%)	87(93.5%)	0.674
Female	1(4.2%)	23(95.8%)	
Total	7(6%)	110(94%)	

Table 5. Stratification of “PACG” with respect to gender

Age (Years)	Secondary Glaucoma		P value
	Yes	No	
30-50	5(10.2%)	44(89.8%)	0.387
51-70	4(5.9%)	64(94.1%)	
Total	9(7.7%)	108(92.3%)	

Table 6. Stratification of “Secondary Glaucoma” with respect to age

Gender	Secondary Glaucoma		P value
	Yes	No	
Male	6(6.5%)	87(93.5%)	0.321
Female	4(5.9%)	21(87.5%)	
Total	9(7.7%)	108(92.3%)	

Table 7. Stratification of “Secondary Glaucoma” with respect to gender

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DISCUSSION

In this research study, the study sample was nationally diverse, and was represented by gender, age, area of residence (rural or urban). The response rate was significant, and thus the results can be generalized to the whole province of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. However, the population is currently genetically diverse to a certain point. Our sample probably has the same genetic predisposition for “glaucoma” as seen in “Asian populations”. Pakistan’s prevalence of “glaucoma” is comparable to that of “Temba, South Africa” (16), and is mildly greater than “South African Zulus” (17) and “Kongwa, Tanzania” (18), however lesser than “Tema, Ghana” (19) and “Akinyele, SW Nigeria” (20). Despite the samples of these studies being local, there appears to be surfacing trend, with the prevalence being greater in “West Africa” as compared to “South Africa”, which itself is greater than in “East Africa”. Comparing the “Ghana study” (19) to our local study; there was a great number of “Level 1 diagnosis” (87.2 %) ,and there were greater number of cataracts and other pathologies which prevented visual field examination. Pakistan also has greater prevalence of “glaucoma” compared to “Brazil” (21), “Iran” (22), indigenous populations in “Australia” (23) and Qatar (24). Geographical and ethnic differences in prevalence have been linked to variations in “genetic and environmental” factors (25,26).

Glaucoma’s classification based on the pathophysiology involved and also on the angle morphological features is imperative, as “POAG” and “PACG” have different disease manifestations, treatments and prognosis. The commonest type of ‘glaucoma’ in Pakistan was ‘POAG’; with a similar trend in other populations (20,21).

In this research study, “POAG” was found to be in 34.2% of the patients, “PACG” in 6%, and “Secondary Glaucoma” was in 7.7% in a total of 117 participants. Comparing it to a different study, which showed that the frequency of POAG was 30.5%, PACG 5.1% and “Secondary glaucoma” was 7.8% in a total of 682 patients with glaucoma (12).

Similarly, another study showed that the frequency of “primary open angle glaucoma (POAG)” was 1.7%, “primary angle-closure glaucoma (PACG)” 1.5% and “Secondary glaucoma” was 0.8% in a total of 691 patients suspected of having glaucoma (13). Published studies regarding glaucoma in multiple populations have differed widely in several aspects, such as, the advancement and availability of different instruments used in the study; instruments which were used for measurements at one time might have been different

from those used for repeat testing (such as, that of a “visual field test”). The publications can also have varied in monetary aspects and other logistical resources, such as availability of support staff and examiners. Certain techniques can be used to evaluate optic disk cupping such as; using slit lamp for binocular indirect ophthalmoscopy including the use of eye piece. Other techniques include the use of scanning laser ophthalmoscope, disk photography and direct ophthalmoscopy. Hence the specific order of examination can help in organizing such studies in complete way.

One cannot state for sure whether differences in methodology might have significant effects on the estimated prevalence, keeping in mind the standard definition. However, this could be addressed by meticulous analysis of all old and newer studies to come, in which different methodological approaches are used and comparisons established. For conventional standards, there are some other instruments that can be used as a substitute such as Humphrey field analyzer (HFA).

An important aspect to bring into consideration is the reliability of these tests. Standards of trial checks offered by the “Zeiss-Humphrey” might not be up to the mark. Fixation loss scores can have insignificant accuracy or precision also they also can be sensitive in blind spot plotting in wrong way. Considering the data, the false negative and positive indices are also imprecise. The false negative rate can be between 14% and 52% given the 95% confidence interval around a 32.8% rate of false negatives. A few enhancements were done to the software in HFA machine to calculate false positive and negative rate but there is a limitation in availability of it for independent calculation. Also note, in developing countries, due to exclusion of field testing there is less reporting on prevalence of glaucoma.

Although this method is not conclusive, but the intent of this method is to identify the proportion of patients who are suffering from vision loss due to glaucoma. It also helps us in identifying the cause of disease. Further research and clinical studies are required to validate the merits of this proposed system.

CONCLUSION

Most common glaucoma in our local population is POAG. A high proportion of PACG and secondary glaucoma were caused by different cataract procedures. Males were affected more compared to females in all types of glaucoma.

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